

Studies in the Synthesis of Cyclohexenocoumarins: Part II.

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α -Naphthol on succinylation furnished β -1-(4-hydroxynaphthoyl) propionic acid, which on Clemmensen reduction gave γ -1-(4-hydroxynaphthyl) butyric acid. The acid on Pechmann reaction with ethylacetoacetate gave 4-methyl-7,8-benzocoumarin-6-butyric acid as well as its ethyl ester. The above acid on cyclisation with PPA gave 4-methyl-4'-ketcyclohexeno (5', 6', 5, 6)benzo (h) coumarin. 4-Methyl and 4-phenyl derivatives of cyclohexeno (h) coumarin were also synthesised by the condensation of ar-tetrahydro- α -naphthol with ethylacetoacetate and ethylbenzoylacetate.

Earlier we reported the synthesis of 7-methoxy-4-methyl-4'-ketcyclohexeno (5', 6', 5, 6) coumarin¹. The present work deals with the synthesis of 4-methyl-4'-ketcyclohexeno (5', 6', 5, 6) benzo (h) coumarin (I) and 4-methyl and 4-phenyl derivatives of cyclohexeno (h) coumarin (II).

α -Naphthol was succinylated in a similar manner to resorcinol with succinic anhydride in nitrobenzene in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride. Contrary to the reported² unsuccessful attempt to do so, we had no difficulty in the above condensation. The assigned β -1-(4-hydroxy-naphthoyl)-propionic acid structure (IIa) to the product was confirmed by its conversion to (IIIb) and hydrolysis of the latter to known³ (IIIc).

On Clemmensen reduction, β -1-(4-hydroxynaphthoyl) propionic acid gave γ -1-(4-hydroxynaphthyl) butyric acid which on Pechmann reaction with ethyl acetoacetate and concentrated sulphuric acid furnished the 4-methyl-7, 8-benzocoumarin-6-butyric acid (IVa) and its ethyl ester (IVb). The structure of the latter was proved by esterification of the former with ethanol and concentrated sulphuric acid and also by its hydrolysis to (IVa).

4-Methyl-7, 8-benzocoumarin-6-butyric acid on cyclisation with polyphosphoric acid gave 4-methyl-4'-keto-cyclohexeno (5', 6', 5, 6) benzo (h) coumarin (I).

We also report here the synthesis of 4-methyl cyclohexeno (h) coumarin (IIa) and 4-phenyl-cyclohexeno (h) coumarin (IIb) from ar-tetrahydro- α -naphthol, prepared according to Bamberger and Brodt⁵, and ethylacetoacetate and ethylbenzoylacetate using concentrated sulphuric acid as condensing agent. It may be mentioned that α - and β -naphthacoumarins, their methyl derivatives as well as their reduced products have been reported as potent anthelmintic agents.⁴

1. Part I. *This Journal*, 1966, **43**, 801.
2. R. D. Desai and V. H. Shroff, *J. Univ. Bombay*, 1941, **10**, pt. 3, 97; *C.A.*, 1942, **36**, 3795.
3. L. Ruzicka and H. Waldmann, *Helv. Chim. Acta.*, 1932, **15**, 907.
4. T. Nakabayasi, *Yakugaku Zasshi.*, 1957, **77**, 544; *Chem. Abstr.*, 1957, **51**, 14709.
5. E. Bamberger and F. Brodt., *Ber.*, 1890, **23**, 215.

EXPERIMENTAL

Succinoylation of α -naphthol :

β -1-(4-Hydroxynaphthoyl) propionic acid (IIIa): α -Naphthol (14.4 g; 0.1M) and succinic anhydride (12.8; 0.12M) were mixed together with dry nitrobenzene (20 ml.). Anhydrous aluminium chloride (26.8 g; 0.2M) dissolved in nitrobenzene was added to the above mixture and was left for 15 hr at the room temperature with the calcium chloride guard tube.

I

IV a. R = H

b. R = C₂H₅

The paste obtained by usual work up was purified through bicarbonate solution. It was crystallised from hot water in shining crystals, m.p. 230°. Yield 5.5 g. It gave green colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution. (Found : C, 68.73; H, 4.94. C₁₄H₁₂O₄ requires C, 68.84; H, 4.95%.)

β -1-(4-Hydroxynaphthoyl) propionic acid (0.1*M*) on refluxion with dimethylsulphate (0.2*M*) and anhydrous potassium carbonate in acetone for 5 to 6 hr. gave a pasty product which was directly hydrolysed to β -1-(4-methoxy-naphthoyl) propionic acid by warming with dilute sodium hydroxide solution for 2 hr. The compound on crystallisation from alcohol gave (IIIc) shining needles, m.p. 171°. The mixed m.p. with the compound prepared by succinylation of the methyl ether of α -naphthol according to Ruzicka *et al*³ was not depressed.

Clemmensen reduction of β -1-(4-hydroxynaphthoyl) propionic acid: γ -1-(4-Hydroxynaphthyl) butyric acid: β -1-(4-Hydroxynaphthoyl) propionic acid (10 g) was mixed with dioxan (10 ml.), water (15 ml.) and con. hydrochloric acid (50 ml.). The mixture was boiled and zinc amalgam (20 g) was added at some intervals and the refluxion was continued for 15 hr. After every 5 hr interval con. hydrochloric acid (5 ml.) was added. The solution was cooled, ether extracted and the paste obtained after evaporation of the ether was crystallised from hot water in shining crystals, m.p. 144°. Yield 3.4 g. It gave violet colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution. (Found : C, 72.71; H, 6.17. $C_{14}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 73.02; H, 6.13%.)

4-Methyl-7, 8-benzocoumarin-6-butyric acid (IVa). γ -1-(4-Hydroxynaphthyl) butyric acid (2.30 g; 0.01*M*) was mixed with ethylacetoacetate (1.3 g.; 0.01*M*) and to the cooled solution, concentrated sulphuric acid (80%; 15 ml.) was slowly added. Usual work up yielded (0.5 g.) product, crystallised from acetic acid in colourless crystals, m.p. 207°. (Found : C, 72.91; H, 5.66. $C_{18}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 72.90; H, 5.44%.)

Ethyl-4-methyl-7, 8-benzocoumarin-6-butyrate (IVb). In the above Pechmann reaction the bicarbonate insoluble product was found to be the ester of the acid which was crystallised from acetic acid in colourless needles, m.p. 130°. Yield 0.1 g. The same ester was also prepared by esterification of the acid with ethanol and concentrated sulphuric acid. M.p. and mixed m.p. was 130°. (Found : C, 73.98; H, 5.98. $C_{20}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 74.05; H, 6.22%.)

4-Methyl-4'-ketocyclohexeno (5', 6', 5, 6) benzo (*h*) coumarin (I): 4-Methyl-7-8-benzocoumarin-6-butyric acid (0.5 g.) was cyclised by heating it with polyphosphoric acid (5 g.) at 160° for 30 min. The mixture was decomposed in ice water, filtered and washed with bicarbonate solution. The compound was crystallised from glacial acetic acid in yellow shining needles, m.p. 220°. Yield 0.1 g. (Found : C, 77.72; H, 5.08. $C_{18}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 77.68; H, 5.07%.)

ar-Tetrahydro-1-naphthol: It was prepared by reducing α -naphthol with sodium, and amyl alcohol according to Bamberger and Brodt⁵.

4-Methylcyclohexeno (*h*) coumarin (IIa): *ar*-Tetrahydro-1-naphthol (1.48 g; 0.01*M*) was mixed with ethyl acetoacetate (1.3 g.; 0.01*M*). The mixture was cooled in ice bath and concentrated sulphuric acid (80%; 6 ml) was added to it slowly with shaking. The crude product obtained by conventional work up was washed with dilute alkali solution and crystallised from alcohol in colourless shining plates, m.p. 125°. (Found : C, 78.25; H, 6.57. $C_{14}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 78.48; H 6.59%.)

4-Phenylcyclohexeno (h) coumarin (IIb) : ar-Tetrahydro-1-naphthol on similar condensation with ethyl benzoylacetate with the above mentioned condition furnished 4-phenyl cyclohexeno (h) coumarin which on crystallisation from ethanol gave greenish shining crystals m.p.151°. (Found : C,82.30; H, 5.89. $C_{19}H_{16}O_2$ requires C,82.56; H,5.83%)

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